

Consumers' Perception towards Chines Smart Brand Phone TECNO

Author's Details:

Mohammad Wasay Abbasi

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: wasayabbasi@hotmail.com

Dr. Masood Hassan

PhD, IoBM, Karachi, Pakistan and Visiting Faculty Greenwich, Karachi, Pakistan,

Email: masoodhassan1@hotmail.com (**Corresponding Author**)

Ali Ashad Siddiqui

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: siddiquiali439@gmail.com

Hamza Aijaz

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: hamzaaijaz95@gmail.com

Haris Khan

Scholar, Greenwich University, Karachi, Pakistan. Email: kharis316@gmail.com

Abstract

In this study paper for Greenwich University, quantitative research was conducted using hypothesis testing along with Statistical tools to find out consumer's perception and buying behavior towards the Chinese Mobile phone brand – TECNO. TECNO, which was founded in 2006, arrived in Pakistan 11 years later; 2017. TECNO has always adhered to the motto "Think Globally, Act Locally" by developing smart gadgets that are tailored to the unique requirements of distinct geographic areas. By offering multi-sensory devices that are ideal for rich visual and aural effects, it has elevated its degree of popularity among young people. Even though consumer perception and buying behavior are two separate ideas, they are connected and are both crucial when conducting consumer research. Consumer perception is the process by which consumers select, organize, and interpret inputs to produce an insightful and persuasive understanding of the outside world. Whereas the study of consumer actions when deciding whether to buy a product that satisfies their wants is known as buying behavior. It is a study of consumer behavior and what drives people to buy and utilize products. For marketers, understanding & studying consumer purchasing behavior and their underlying perception about a brand is essential because it enables them to know what their target market wants from them. Research method chosen for this paper was solely quantitative. Data collection, population, sample size and statistics were collected, analyzed, and interpreted from Karachi based citizens. By studying the numerical and statistical data supplied in this research from the responses of various consumers and retailers of TECNO, there will be an increase in the present understandings of the Pakistani mobile makers & wholesalers who are producing sections of TECNO in Pakistan. It will provide them with a clear image of where TECNO stands in the market, allowing them to improve its features or make some changes to increase TECNO's acceptance in Pakistan. The results obtained from this research were in high correlation with the independent variables considered under hypothesis testing. Customer's social-economic status, brand quality, brand image, brand loyalty are all the factors which heavily affects consumer's perception and buying behavior towards a brand.

Keywords: Perception, Consumer, Chinese, Smart Phone, TECNO.

Introduction

Over the period Pakistan has emerged as one of the markets for smartphones, and with the increase in technology there has been a significant increase in the sale of smartphones in Pakistan. The accession of the technology of mobile broadband has been remarkably increasing in Pakistan along with the adoption of smartphones which further makes Pakistan's mobile market as on the fastest growing in region. As stated by PTA (Pakistan Telecommunication Authority) almost forty-two million people of Pakistan are using 3G/4G services in Pakistan (Ahmed, 2017). However, along with the increasing use of smartphones in Pakistan it is also important to note that how consumers perceive specific smartphone brands and how successful are these brands in their target market. Similar is the purpose of this report, specifically chosen TECNO, a Chinese smartphone brand which is an affordable one and regarded as, "Budget King" of the Pakistani mobile market. It is generally famous as it provides number of specifications and reliability at a very low price, its phones are available in the range of RS 20,000 which is affordable for our mediocre society. Furthermore, according to

some reports, it is among top five most sold brands in the Pakistani mobile market (Shabir, 2021). Moreover, TECNO'S market share is the third highest as of July 2022 which is 12.87 percent (Counter, 2020). as the smartphones that fall in the range of Rs 10,000 to Rs 20,000 are sold the most in Pakistan because of the factor of affordability. More than 35 percent of the Pakistani smartphone users carry low-cost phone for safety reasons of affordability factor (Ahmed, 2017).

This study and research paper analyzes the awareness of consumers, acceptance and perception regarding TECNO mobile phone brand. As per the reports, majority of Pakistani people who buy phones are already aware about this smartphone brand "TECNO", the rest 20-25 percent are either not fully aware of the brand name or their features, or they have no acceptance towards the brand as by the time TECNO entered the market, Gen Z was already drawn towards the mobile phones brand that were long established in the markets such as Samsung and iPhone. However, because of the affordability factor the market share for these phones is low. Additionally, TECNO made its place in the Pakistani mobile market in 2020 when it acquired the rank of second most selling mobile phone brand in Pakistan, as stated by the IDC's "Handsets Summary Pakistan", it sold 16.5 percent units of all the brand share of smartphones in Pakistan (Desk, 2020).

Pakistan's mobile market has a large amount of untapped potential, but its existing levels of smartphone adoption, mobile internet use, and digital service use are lower than those of other nations in the area. In its most recent report, "The Mobile Economy Asia Pacific 2021," the GSMA, which represents the interests of mobile operators worldwide and unites more than 750 operators with almost 400 companies in the broader mobile ecosystem, claims that certain policy decisions may have hampered Pakistan's digital development and growth of the online economy (Amin, 2021). Chinese mobile phone manufacturers have been essential in assisting Pakistan avoid mobile phone imports in 2021.

This study aims to examine consumer awareness, acceptability, perception, and purchasing patterns toward the Chinese smartphone brand "TECNO" and explore the mobile phone retailers' perspective on this brand. We will employ various quantitative research techniques such as creating online polls, making surveys, and designing questionnaires by Google forms to obtain statistical, measurable, and accurate information about TECNO & it's brand preference in the Pakistani market.

Significance of Research

By analyzing the numerical and statistical data presented in this research from the responses of various consumers and retailers of TECNO, there will be an increment in the present understandings of the Pakistani mobile manufacturers & wholesalers who are developing parts of TECNO in Pakistan. It will give them a clear-cut picture of how TECNO stands in the market, hence they would be able to enhance its features or make some amendments to make a wider acceptability of TECNO in Pakistan.

Specifically, this research will also benefit other local mobile manufacturers of how they could rightfully target their customers and make their mobile brand stand out the most by working on its features, RAM, storage capacity, screen size, battery life and camera results.

Moreover, the results presented in this research through descriptive statistics, tables, graphs, and charts will also serve as a tool to further perform such studies in the future by other researchers.

Literature Review

Consumer's Social Economic Class

First independent variable is social-economic class of a consumer which constantly impacts the consumer perception and their buying behavior towards a brand. To understand, how these independent variable impacts perception of consumers and their buying behaviors, it is necessary to first understand the term social-economic class of a consumer. Social class refers to a segment in the society which is determined by a hierarchy of the classification for individuals and families along with a definite status. It comprises of classes as classified by Warner into six categories including, Upper Upper class, Lower Upper class, Upper Middle Class, Lower Middle Class, Upper Lower Class, and Lower Lower Class (WHAT IS A SOCIAL CLASS - CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR, 2021). Socio-economic class or status is most likely to be measured through a combination of

varied factors of an individual's life such as education, occupation, income, savings, and others. (Socioeconomic Status, 2019). It is important to examine socio economic status as it most of the time reveals different issues such as issued in relation to privilege, control, and power. A social-economic class of an individual may also be determined through the amount of status, more specifically the status members of society possess when compared to the members of different social classes.

Brand Quality

Brand quality refers to the perception regarding the quality of a specific product or brand that it attains with its consumers. It is mostly defined as being up to the consumer's expectations (Spacey, 2015). Brand quality holds considerable amount of importance in people's daily life. Products and services are able to give top quality objectively, as judged, for example, by the conclusions of professional analyses of scientific testing. However, regardless of objective data, customers will not buy items if they do not believe they are superior goods that meet their wants and give value. Customers' associations with the offers serve as a range of sensory signals that determine the brand quality of goods and services. These cues might be either external or internal to the item or service. Such indications, either individually or together, provide the ground for evaluations of the goods and services (Wisnblit, 2015).

Brand Image

Brand image refers to what customers or consumers perceive and think of a specific brand, it is kind of an image that a consumer has in their minds, it can also be elucidated as a brand's perception that customers possess in their minds. This image keeps on developing over a period on different basis such as interconnectivity and experience that a consumer has had with the brand. These activities of interconnectivity may take place in different forms and may not always involve the use or purchase of products and services. Brand images possess significant importance as it is helpful in fulfillment of the business motives of a company and it has number of advantages (Pahwa, 2022).

Brand Loyalty

Brand loyalty is another important aspect and independent variable that impacts consumer perception and their buying behavior. It is an important part of research and researchers emphasize their focus on the loyalty of customers towards the already existing brands. the loyalty of a customer with a brand is when the customers repeatedly and consistently choose the products or services of one brand over their competitors. It is important to understand as when a consumer is loyal towards one brand, they are not easily convinced by other brands' availability, price, quality, or image. Customers would instead pay more and make certain the similar quality service and product that they have already experience and are aware of. With the help of customer's brand loyalty, the brands and companies become compatible with the expectations of customers and even tend to exceed them (Chambers, 2020).

Consumer Perception and Buying Behavior Towards a Brand

Consumer perception and buying behavior are two entirely different concepts but they are interconnected and the two are considered incredibly important when doing consumer research. Consumer perception is the method by which consumers choose, arrange, and interpret inputs to create a meaningful and cogent view of the outside world. Even though two individuals could be exposed to the identical stimulus, how each person's ability to notice, choose, arrange, and interpret these stimuli is extremely individualized and is dependent on their own needs, expectations, and values. Consumers respond and behave based on perceptions rather than facts. "Reality" is a completely individualized concept for each person. A phenomenon considering their own needs, desires, beliefs, and life experiences. hence, customer perceptions about a brand are considerably more important to marketers than their understanding of the truth as it is (Wisnblit, 2015).

Since the 1970s, McCain's trademark has been a signature in a rectangular black box that communicated the brand's skill in freezing technology. McCain is the top supplier of frozen chips in the UK. The brand stood in

for the developments in household innovation, much like the microwave and vacuum cleaner, which are icons of contemporary convenience. However, a resurgence of curiosity about the origins and production of food led McCain to start explaining to consumers "the supply behind the procedure," assuring them that McCain chips are simply potatoes that have been chopped up in sunflower oil before cooking. This communication got off to a strong start with the popular advertising campaign "It's all okay," but more needed to be done. McCain worked with the strategic design agency Brand Opus to create a new visual brand. The CEO of Brand Opus, Nir Wegrzyn, said: "McCain pushed us to give their brand identity new significance. The name McCain now represents real, natural, nutritious food instead of being associated with the frigid freezer aisle. "The new visual identity establishes the sunshine as the new symbol for the brand and reflects the warmth and positivity of the natural world that McCain products originate from," said Helen Priestley, director of marketing for McCain. Figure A shows consumers' perceptions of the new and old brand identities and Figure B features the old package on the left side and the new one on the right (Wisnblit, 2015) (McCain, 2022).

Customer perceptions about a firm, its products or brands, and services have a significant impact on consumer buying habits. To positively sway the impressions of their target customers, firms invest a lot of money in self-promotion, improving customer service, and other measures. A company may affect such impressions and encourage lucrative consumer behaviors by carefully planning and carrying out its operations (Mack, 2019). Consumer buying behavior is the study of consumers' actions when selecting whether to purchase an item that meets their needs. It is an investigation into how customers behave and what motivates them to purchase and use goods. The study of consumer purchasing behavior is crucial for marketers because it helps them comprehend what customers anticipate from them. Understanding what prompts a consumer to purchase a product is useful. To introduce a product to the market, it is critical to determine the kind of products that buyers want. Marketers can comprehend what consumers enjoy and detest so they may create their marketing strategies accordingly (Clootrack, 2022). According to (Lamb C. , 2003) and (Rowley, 2001) , there are four kinds of consumer buying behaviors i.e., Extensive Decision-Making, Limited Decision-Making, Habitual Buying Behavior or Routine Response, and Impulsive buying. These four kinds of buying behavior indicates the relationship of customer with the brand; these behaviors can range from highly loyal to no loyal customers at all.

Extensive Decision Making

Extensive Decision making is done for expensive goods and occasional purchases (Anderson, 2015) describes Extensive decision making as an indulged decision-making process. This means consumers consider a variety of time for looking for the right product, there is high involvement, higher thinking process and critical decision making involved with a pinch of emotional decision making. They demand a lot of work, frequently include unknown companies or items, and need extensive research to assure consumer confidence (KLEIDERLY, 2022). For instance, if you go to look for a fridge then it is a high involvement product with risky purchase and would need extensive decision making by the consumer. Another example can be that people do not purchase a sizable flat-screen television every day, so when the time comes to invest in anything of this kind, we want to be certain that we are selecting the ideal brand and image quality. Major purchases have a higher level of risk for the buyer, which increases the need to think things through carefully. One would typically seek advice from friends and family, learn as much as one can about different specs, and spend a significant amount of time reading for product reviews and testimonies rather than grabbing the first television one sees or purchasing one simply because it is on sale (Okoli, 2020) (Boundless.com, 2022).

Limited Decision Making

Choosing between mid-priced goods, purchases that are made sometimes, or purchases from a brand that is recognizable to some extent, is known as limited decision making. They need a small amount of effort and possibly some research. Although they are familiar with the product in this sort of decision-making, consumers still need additional information to make sure it meets their demands (Rani, 2014). It applies to things like apparel, furniture, and gadgets that are occasionally purchased. Additionally, consumers conduct research, make

comparisons, and spend a reasonable amount of time to decide before purchasing such things. Clothing is among the most eminent instances of how businesses may sway consumers looking for items with little decision-making requirements (Bhasin, 2018). Through social media management, e-retailers like Shien and Myntra strive to increase customer involvement. In addition, they emphasize consumer-focused activities to build mutually beneficial connections with their customers and sway their choices. For instance, the British online retailer ASOS has placed a strong emphasis on user-generated content strategy to increase consumer involvement with programs like #AsSeenOnMe (ASOS, 2019).

Habitual Buying Behavior

Habitual buying behavior also known as routine response plays a key role in our daily routine. When purchasing a product that is both absurdly inexpensive and widely accessible, we do not give it any thought or consideration. In this kind of purchasing scenario, decision-making is not contingent on critical thought. The buyer has previously had a lot of experience with the product in this decision-making category (Sharma, 2014). Customers therefore use this form of purchasing decisions while making regular purchases. In addition to brand awareness, product quality is an important consideration. Additionally, consumers engage in routine response buying for items like food that have a lower price tag (Anderson, 2015). Consider how regularly one might purchase new socks. Either one consistently loses them, or one constantly winds up with holes in them. Since one is constantly running out of socks, he/she keeps purchasing the one pair that costs the least amount of money. He/she really developed a habit out of it (KLEIDERLY, 2022). The reason for a customer's habitual purchasing behavior may also be that they find the product to be the greatest match for their needs and continue to purchase it without exploring for alternatives. And it does not imply that the client has less options and must decide anyway. Because the product does not differ significantly from others, the buyer consistently picks it without thinking about it. Habit purchasing is the term for repeated purchases. Additionally, the things they buy are inexpensive and safe to acquire (Team, 2021) (OpenLearn, 2017) .

Impulsive Buying

Impulsive buying takes place when customers make unplanned purchases of goods or services. Emotions and sentiments are major triggers for this kind of purchasing behavior (Badgaiyan & Verma, 2014). Uncertainty on the part of the customer as to their requirements and wants is one situation that might lead to impulsive purchase. In many instances, a display or advertisement in-store may persuade the customer to make a purchase. Impulsive purchasing is difficult to classify under any one product category, however it is most frequently seen with items like mobile phones, technological devices, clothing, and expensive goods like jewelry. Irrational thinking frequently leads to spontaneous and unforeseen purchases, which are frequently preyed upon by strategists. Impulsive purchasing is sparked by environments that encourage browsing, in-store displays, celebrity endorsements, and discounted items. (Rowley, 2001) “[...] *impulse buying occurs when a consumer experiences a sudden, often powerful, and persistent urge to buy something immediately. The impulse to buy is hedonically complex and may stimulate emotional conflict. Also, impulse buying is prone to occur with diminished regard for its consequences*” (Rook, 1987).

A comparison of the four diverse types of buying behavior i.e., routine response (also known as habitual buying), limited decision making, extensive decision making, and impulsive decision making is shown in the table below:

Table No.1:*Comparison of the four buying behaviors*

	Routine response	Limited decision making	Extensive decision making	Impulsive
Involvement	Low	Low to moderate	High	Low
Time	Short	Short to moderate	Long	Short
Cost	Low	Low to moderate	High	Low to moderate
Information search	Internal	Mostly internal	Internal and external	External
Number of alternatives	One	Few	Many	Many

Table source: (Lamb & McDaniel, 2011).

Consumer's Social Economic Class & Consumer Perception and Buying Behavior Towards a Brand

It is important to understand how both aspects are related and how the independent variable influences the other. The social classes of an individual play a key role in influencing a consumer. In same social class there are people who have similar behavior, values, and lifestyle. As for the marketer or researcher it is important to pay more attention here as buying behavior of individuals in same social class tends to be alike, however the level of influence may vary from high to low. For marketer, this has different implications as he can conduct his activities of marketing in accordance with the distinct social classes (Fisher, 1987)

Another important attribute that falls under social classes is social perception which tends to be influencing the individual's buying behavior. For instance, when a person who belongs to a group that earns lower income may have his major focus towards the price when he makes purchases. On the other hand, a person who belongs to an income group that earns high may be more concerned about the quality and authenticity of the product (Haymond, 2022). Moreover, there are also different situations that needs to be considered by a researcher to properly determine the relationship, such as a situation where an individual is more influenced by a group that he is not related to but desires to be a part of it (Influence of Culture & Social Class, 2021). Furthermore, the research for independent variable social economic class shows that consumers who belong to lower social economic class do not willingly pay more price for the brands or products they desire than those of people who belong to high income group. Variables that belong to low socio-economic status including little income affects the attitude that individuals possess in that group.

Brand Quality & Consumer Perception and Buying Behavior Towards a Brand

Brand quality is one of the important independent variables that impacts the perceptions of consumers and their buying behavior towards brand. To understand how both are related and how brand quality is impacting the consumer perception, we first need to have a clear image about the brand quality in our minds, as this section of study aims to investigate the relationship between both. As discussed earlier, brand quality refers to the perception regarding the quality of a specific product or brand that it attains with its consumers. It is mostly defined as being up to the consumers expectations (Spacey, 2015).

Additionally, brand quality is also referred as how the quality of product is recognized which strongly influences the purchasing behavior of consumers. The impact that quality of brands has on its intention of purchase has been verified in many studies which also lead to results that the brand quality has both positive

and negative impacts on the intention of purchasing of consumers (Takeuchi & Quelch, 1983). Brand quality plays a significant role as it provides convenience to consumers and they know to what limit the expectations should be set up towards the experience of a brand. Brand quality also tends to impact the profitability of a company. Brand quality is related to consumer perception in a way that it builds trust among consumers, by offering brand quality the consumer loyalty and trust is gained and consumers trust more in what brand has to offer. Moreover, it also leads to recommendations as word of mouth is one of the strongest ways to influence consumers, if consumers' expectation about brand quality is met, they will consider purchasing again and recommending the product to others (Caramela, 2022).

It is the most common observation that when brand quality is up to the expectations of consumers, they tend to repurchase from the same brand repeatedly. Hence, we know how important branding is to determine consumer buying behavior and perception, we as individuals go through times where we buy products from a specific brand because of their quality.

Brand Image & Consumer Perception and Buying Behavior Towards a Brand

With the passing time every producer and brand attempts to make themselves different and distinct from other brands of the similar product. These are the evolving marketing techniques as the study gave details, in old days differentiation among the brands or products were only a sign, mark or even a number (Cantor, 2019). To have distinct nature the brands then tend to create contrasting functions such as brand image that not only creates the value for a brand in the minds of consumers but also end up creating a unique coalition and memory link in the minds. Additionally, it also creates hype and demand for a brand's goods and services as it tends to attract the customer while creating awareness about the product the brand makes (Ashraf, Naeem, & Shahzadi, 2017).

Through brand image a brand successfully creates a unique place in the minds of consumers for their product which further preserve and attracts customers. This brand image and unique place also creates the perception regarding brand in the minds of consumers (Keller, 2000). Consumers anticipate more things from a brand's products before using it only through the brand image. It is also important to note that brand image tends to be both positive and negative, in many cases it creates whole new number of consumers and helps to build more strong customer relationships with them and maintain loyalty. Whereas, if the brand image is negative it leads to no repetition and retention of consumers and it further harms the business (Thompson, 2022).

Thus, we know how important branding is to determine consumer buying behavior and perception, even we go through situations where we buy products just because it looks attractive. It is natural for humans to be congenial when they make right decisions, this is how brand image works and impacts the buying behavior of consumers (Samuel, 2021).

Brand Loyalty & Consumer Perception and Buying Behavior Towards a Brand

Brand loyalty impacts the perception of consumers and their buying behavior as it reinforces their buying habits. In most of the situations, the purchases that consumers make are based on their habit as most of the consumers make repeated purchases (Wood, 2009). In spite of, different alternatives and competitors of the same product and the product fitting their needs, consumers tend to be less interested in experimenting or trying out new brands because the process of trying out and becoming aware of a new brand's product takes time and requires decision making, and as humans we tend to avoid the chances of being disappointed or wasting time or money on a product that is inferior which are high when trying out new products (Haley, Hughes, & Klompmaker, 1976).

This is how the consumer's loyalty impacts the buying behavior of consumers, it is grinding to attract the consumers towards a new brand who are already loyal to an existing brand. Furthermore, consumers who are already hooked on one brand will also continue to make purchases from the same brand anyway of price or convenience. As brand loyalty is a factor that is strong enough factor that stops consumer to switch to an alternative brand (How Brand Loyalty Affects Consumer Behaviour?, 2022).

Thus, this part of the research study shows that a loyal consumer is difficult to attract, and it is a major factor that impacts the buying behavior of consumers towards a brand, as a loyal consumer would not want to try out

or shift towards latest brands. For a brand there are implications and important to study the consumer loyalty aspect in detail.

Methodology

Research Design

A research design is a strategy for addressing the central issues raised by the study (QuestionPro, 2022). The research design for a quantitative dissertation will focus on gathering and analyzing numerical data. Decision must be made whether the dissertation will be exploratory or conclusive before finalizing the specifics of the quantitative research design. Exploratory research aims to produce broad insights by thoroughly examining the topic. Contrarily, conclusive research seeks to get a firm conclusion on the subject (Organizing Academic Research Papers: Types of Research Designs, 2022). This quantitative research was exploratory as it was the first time such data has been collected merely for the purpose of analyzing consumer perception and buying behavior towards TECNO. Additionally, case studies and examined literature presented various techniques used to achieve the intended outcomes. Following that, non-probability sampling was used to create the observations, surveys, and questionnaire designs for a specific population sample. The consistency of the obtained outcomes and data is also evaluated for reliability. There are many types of quantitative research designs but the one utilized for this study was a combination of the two approaches i.e., quasi-experimental and experimental (Edu, 2021).

A cause-and-effect connection between one variable and another is sought after in a quasi-experimental quantitative research design. One of the variables in this study is independent, while the other is dependent. The dependent variable's value, however, is entirely dependent on changes in the independent variable and is not affected by the other variables in any way. (Grand Canyon University, 2021) Likewise, this study utilized this approach and identified the cause-and-effect relationship of the dependent and the independent variables. Socio-economic class of a customer, brand quality & image, and customer's existing brand loyalty with their preferred brands were all the independent variables which significantly affected the dependent variable of the study; customer's perception and buying behavior towards TECNO. However, quasi-experimental study is not a real experimental study because it does not assign study participants to groups randomly. Instead, it places them in certain categories based on a characteristic they share or non-random criteria they satisfy. Hence, experimental approach as considered to form a more reliable and realistic quantitative results for this research.

The scientific method is applied in experimental quantitative research design. It sets protocols that enable the researcher to put a hypothesis to the test and to investigate causal links methodically and objectively between variables. Three fundamental phases are present in all experimental quantitative research projects. The researcher first measures the factors. The researcher then modifies or affects the variables in some way. To determine how the intervention influenced the variables, the researcher next remeasures the variables. (Grand Canyon University, 2021) The features of the experimental quantitative study in this research are as follows:

- The variables' characteristics and connections
- Applicable testable hypotheses
- Using pre-established criteria, subjects were divided into groups.
- Treatments that alter the independent variable in experiments

This quantitative research primarily focused on TECNO mobile brand identified the dependent and independent variables by developing statistical questionnaires and surveys. The hypotheses and conceptual framework were also tested and observed by forming questionnaires and surveys for the consumers as well as retailers of TECNO.

Questionnaire Design/Measurement of Constructs

The Questionnaire Design should be made in accordance with the rules of designing a questionnaire. As stated by (Jenn, 2006) a good questionnaire should be accurate, trustworthy, understandable, engaging, and brief. These were the exact features of the questionnaire design for TECNO. It must be ensured that leading or directly addressed questions such as: "Do you like TECNO, or are you satisfied with TECNO's features?"

should be avoided. No two in one question such as: “When you visited mobile shop last time, did you find TECNO and considered buying it?” should be kept in the questionnaire, all such questions should be neglected and must not be included. No amount of extra or high fi English should be used, the questions must be designed in simple and decent vocabulary. It should also be ensured that respondents are able to answer the questions. For instance, questions like; “How many ads have you seen for TECNO in the past month?” should not be asked as it is clear that no proper response could be received from such questions. It should also be made sure that respondents are willing to answer the questions for instance, when asked “what age group you belong to?” A range of options from 18-24 and above must be given so the respondent does not have to specify his/her age in the questionnaire. Hence, questionnaire should be valid, reliable, brief, and succinct (Australian Bureau of Statistics, 2020).

The questionnaire should include all kinds of scales varying from Likert scale, rank-order scale, attitude scales, and even behavior intention scales in order to analyze the socio-economic status of the respondents, their loyalty for existing brands and brand image & quality of TECNO in consumers’ minds. The questionnaire was constructed in order and some of the significant questions asked were as follows:

1. What are you doing currently?
2. Which Phone are you using?
3. Why do you prefer this phone over others?
4. What brands do mobile phone retailers usually recommend to you?
5. If you go to the mobile shop for purchasing a phone, where will your price range fall?
6. Are you aware about the Chinese phone brand “TECNO”?
7. Have you seen tecno on social media?
8. Does TECNO fall into your price range?
9. What class of people do you think would buy TECNO?
10. Are you aware of the product features and services TECNO offers?
11. What would you rate TECNO from a scale of 1-10?

Thus, after asking indirect questions, the respondents were required to answer questions related to TECNO. This is an effective approach for a questionnaire design.

Statistical Techniques

The planning, designing, data collection, analysis, inference of meaningful interpretation, and reporting of the research findings are all statistical approaches used in a study. The statistical analysis lends meaning to the useless data, giving the data some life. Only when appropriate statistical tests are applied will the results and conclusions be accurate. This study aims to familiarize the reader with the fundamental research instruments used while carrying out various investigations. A brief description of the variables, knowledge of quantitative variables, hypotheses, and descriptive statistics are covered in the research (Calvello, 2020)

Data Collection

Major focus of the research and study was towards quantitative data to understand consumer buying behavior and perception, for that purpose primary data was collected through questionnaire and survey, a questionnaire was sent to more than 200 individuals, students, people belonging to different work groups and others so as to learn regarding their perceptions, behavior of buying, buying patterns and awareness that all those individuals had regarding the subject of the study. Furthermore, through this we successfully collected responses of people and interpreted the results. So, for quantitative data the method that was used for collecting data was Questionnaire and Surveys and as the name suggests it included a number of questions directed towards consumer buying behavior. For the survey to be interesting for the respondents, the questions were arranged in a systemized manner and with the help of this, respondents accurately understood and answered the question. Moreover, an accessible audience was chosen who would easily respond the questions. Mostly respondents comprised of acquaintances and social media users. Additionally, short qualitative research was also conducted to understand consumer buying behavior in more detail. For which, the method we used was in depth

interviews. These in-depth interviews were conducted from retailers working in different mobile markets of Karachi and in different areas which further helped in the saturation of data collection.

Population & Sample Size

For the population, people belonging to different Socio-economic classes and work groups from Karachi were selected, they were further broken down into samples and non-probability convenience sampling method was used for the collection of data reason being as the name says this kind of sample is much easier than other methods for the collection of data and individuals that were selected were based on a certain criterion which was awareness of mobile phones or smart phones, in non-probability sampling method not every individual is included in the research, the aim was the development of understanding of a smaller and selected population and to determine consumer buying behavior. Moreover, all the participants in the study of both qualitative and quantitative were from Karachi city. Additionally, questionnaire was shared with nearly 200 people and 104 responses were collected, these respondents aged from 18 years to 25+ and less than 30, belonging to different areas of Karachi majority including Gulshan. In addition, most respondents belonged to Middle Class, Upper Middle or Elite Class and the education level was from O levels/ Matric to bachelor's or Masters.

Furthermore, the second sample was for qualitative research, and the random sampling technique was used as the retailers belonging to different mobile markets were chosen randomly and were taken in-depth interviews of and the mobile markets were also selected randomly. Again, this method was much easier because of the time constraint and there are enormous number of retailers in the Karachi, so to save time random sampling technique was opted for qualitative research. Moreover, the sample size for the retailers was around ten belonging to two different markets of different areas of city, these interviewees belonged to different age groups from 24 to 55 as well and their SEC was Upper Middle Class, Middle Class, or Lower Middle class.

Results

Results obtained through hypothesis testing justified that all the independent variables had a high correlation with the dependent variable. The correlation analysis showed a direct and positive relationship. Firstly, the social-economic status of consumer had a high correlation with consumer's perception & buying behavior towards TECNO. It was evident from observations carried out in the mobile market as well that consumers asked the mobile phone retailers about brands like Apple, Samsung, Oppo and Infinix, it indicated about the consumer's elite and upper-class status. None of them considered buying TECNO even as their secondary phone. Secondly, brand quality also possessed a strong correlation with consumer's perception & buying behavior towards TECNO. Research shows that TECNO's battery drainage problem, camera quality problem makes consumers reluctant towards buying such a phone. Hence, brand quality is a significant factor. Moreover, brand image also significantly impacts and poses a positive relation towards consumer's perception buying behavior regarding TECNO. It is true that brands like Samsung and Apple have maintained a vehement brand image throughout their lives. It will take sufficient time for TECNO to build such a brand image. Lastly, brand loyalty is an also a strong factor possesses a strong relationship with consumer's buying behavior & perception for TECNO. If customers did not develop brand loyalty towards their existing mobile phone brands, they would have made a slight acceptance for purchasing TECNO.

Discussion

The first hypothesis, social economic class and the buying behavior of consumers are related positively as it is observant that people tend to look for brands according to what they can afford and what their social economic class and status is, people belonging to elite or high class prefer more expensive brands than those of middle- or lower-class people. Furthermore, the second hypothesis is about brand quality and its impact on the buying behavior of consumers, both are associated positively with each other, the result also supports that a brand quality may negatively or positively impact the buying behavior of a consumer, as it is a strong independent variable which is most looked for in a brand by consumers. Additionally, third and fourth hypothesis, brand image and brand loyalty are also indicated to have a positive relationship with the buying behavior of

consumers and their perceptions towards a brand as brand loyalty develops more with experience and hence, it impacts consumer buying behavior (Garbarino & Johnson, 1999).

Conclusion

The aim of this research was to conduct in depth analysis of the buying patterns and the perception customers carry in their mind regarding the Chinese mobile phone brand: “TECNO.” The purpose was also to study how significant is the influence of the four independent variables i.e., consumer social economic status, brand quality brand image and brand loyalty upon the dependent variable “consumer’s perception & buying behavior towards TECNO.”

It can be deduced that, the TECNO phone's market and user base are expanding in the lower class, where it is mostly utilized by drivers and housekeepers. To compete with other Chinese manufacturers, TECNO must enhance its features and raise the quality of its phones if it is to continue its position in Pakistan and break into a new market. They need to conduct a suitable marketing effort for rebranding to enter a new market. To convince the customer to purchase the brand's product, TECNO should establish a positive connection with the supplier and provide a large commission. It is evident that brand loyalty, brand image and brand quality play a significant role in building consumer perception and moving them to make a purchase for a brand. The social economic status of a consumer also has an indirect but significant impact upon consumer’s perception towards a brand and the purchasing pattern for it. Even if TECNO is a fully acknowledgeable and known brand it still fails to build the right perception and direct consumers towards making a purchase. Considering the current economic and political situation of Pakistan; it is also true that many mobile phone purchasers are reluctant in buying TECNO or any other mobile phone brand with the increased amount of taxes in mobile phones, many consumers especially the middle class do not even consider going to a mobile phone market.

This quantitative research will assist through examining the numerical and statistical data offered in this research from the replies of various TECNO customers and merchants, the current understandings of Pakistani mobile manufacturers and wholesalers who are manufacturing TECNO components in Pakistan will be enhanced. It would provide them with a clear image of where TECNO stands in the market, allowing them to improve its features or make some changes to increase TECNO's appeal in Pakistan. This research will specifically aid other local mobile producers by demonstrating how they can correctly target their clients and make their mobile brand stand out the most by improving its features, Memory, storage capabilities, screen resolution, power consumption, and photography results.

References

- Ahmed, K. (2017, September 26). Retrieved from <https://dailytimes.com.pk/115257/pakistan-emerges-as-top-market-for-smartphones/>
- Amin, T. (2021). *Mobile industry in Pakistan: Economic contribution can reach '\$24bn' by 2023: GSMA*. Islamabad: breccorder. Retrieved from <https://www.breccorder.com/news/40116879>
- Anderson, D. e. (2015). *An introduction to management science: quantitative approaches to decision making*.
- Ashraf, M., Naeem, M., & Shahzadi, M. (2017). Impact of Branding on Consumer Buying Behavior. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 603. Retrieved from HR Mars: https://hrmars.com/papers_submitted/3124/Impact_of_Branding_on_Consumer_Buying_Behavior.pdf
- ASOS. (2019, 02 28). Retrieved from Get Inspired: <https://www.asos.com/discover/as-seen-on-me/>
- Australian Bureau of Statistics. (2020). Retrieved from <https://www.abs.gov.au/websitedbs/d3310114.nsf/home/Basic+Survey+Design+-+Questionnaire+Design>
- Badgaiyan, & Verma, A. (2014). Intrinsic factors affecting impulsive buying behaviour—Evidence from India. *Journal of Retailing and consumer services*, 537-549. doi: 10.1016/j.jretconser.2014.04.003
- Bhasin, H. (2018, 02 14). *Marketing91*. Retrieved from <https://www.marketing91.com/types-of-decision-process/>

- Boundless.com. (2022). Retrieved from <http://www.library.snls.org.sz/boundless/boundless/definition/extensive-decision-making-buying-behavior/index.html>
- Calvello, M. (2020). 5 Statistical Analysis Methods That Take Data to the Next Level.
- Cantor, A. M. (2019, august 30). *The importance of branding: why branding matters*. Retrieved from 99 designs by vista: <https://99designs.com/blog/logo-branding/importance-of-branding/>
- Caramela, S. (2022, June 29). Retrieved from <https://www.business.com/articles/5-reasons-why-product-quality-matters/>
- Chambers, S. (2020). Retrieved from <https://www.nicereply.com/blog/the-importance-of-customer-loyalty/>
- Clootrack. (2022). Retrieved from https://www.clootrack.com/knowledge_base/what-is-consumer-behavior#:~:text=Consumer%20buying%20behavior%20refers%20to,buy%20and%20use%20certain%20products.
- Counter, S. (2020). Retrieved from <https://gs.statcounter.com/vendor-market-share/mobile/pakistan>
- Desk, W. (2020, November 19). Retrieved from <https://en.dailypakistan.com.pk/19-Nov-2020/tecno-becomes-second-most-selling-brand-in-pakistan#:~:text=According%20to%20the%20IDC's%20%E2%80%9CHandsets,OPPO%2C%20Vivo%2C%20and%20Infinix.>
- Edu, T. L. (2021). Research Design. *Wings*.
- Fisher, J. E. (1987, January 19). *Social Class and Consumer Behavior: the Relevance of Class and Status*. Retrieved from The Association of Consumer Research: <https://www.acrwebsite.org/volumes/6747/volumes/v14/NA%20-%2014>
- Garbarino, E., & Johnson, M. S. (1999). The Different Roles of Satisfaction, Trust, and Commitment in Customer Relationships. *Journal of Marketing*, 87.
- Grand Canyon University. (2021, 12 10). Retrieved from <https://www.gcu.edu/blog/doctoral-journey/quantitative-research-design-methods-writing-dissertations>
- Haley, R. I., Hughes, G. D., & Klompmaker, J. E. (1976). *Test Marketing in Product Development*. Harvard Business Publishing.
- Haymond, A. (2022, September 09). *Effects of Socioeconomic Status on Consumer Behavior and Attitudes Towards a Brand's Image*. Retrieved from University of Nebraska - Lincoln.: <https://digitalcommons.unl.edu/honorstheses/425/>
- How Brand Loyalty Affects Consumer Behaviour? (2022, February 07). Retrieved from drop thought: <https://www.dropthought.com/how-brand-loyalty-affects-consumer-behaviour>
- Influence of Culture & Social Class. (2021, August 24). Retrieved from Tutorials Point: https://www.tutorialspoint.com/consumer_behavior/culture_and_social_class_influence.htm
- Jenn, N. C. (2006). Designing A Questionnaire. *PubMed Central*, 32-35.
- Keller, K. L. (2000, January). *The Brand Report Card*. Retrieved from Harvard Business Review: <https://hbr.org/2000/01/the-brand-report-card>
- Kleiderly. (2022). Retrieved from <https://kleiderly.com/blogs/kleiderly-magazine/the-4-types-of-buying-behaviour>
- Lamb, C. (2003). *Grademaker Sg Marketing*. . New Jersey: Thomson South-Western.
- Lamb, C. H., & McDaniel, C. (2011). MKTG 4. In C. H. Lamb, & C. McDaniel. Mason: Cengage.
- Mack, S. (2019, 03 15). *Chron*. Retrieved from small business.chron: <https://smallbusiness.chron.com/role-perception-consumer-behavior-67136.html>
- McCain*. (2022). Retrieved from <https://www.mccain.com/>
- Okoli, A. (2020). *zoovu.com*. Retrieved from <https://zoovu.com/blog/types-buying-behavior/>
- OpenLearn. (2017). Retrieved from <https://www.open.edu/openlearncreate/mod/oucontent/view.php?id=81567§ion=2.3>
- Organizing Academic Research Papers: Types of Research Designs. (2022). Retrieved from Sacred Heart University: <https://library.sacredheart.edu/c.php?g=29803&p=185902>

- Pahwa, A. (2022). Retrieved from <https://www.feedough.com/brand-image-explanation-examples/>
- QuestionPro. (2022). Retrieved from <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/research-design/>
- Rani, P. (2014). Factors influencing consumer behaviour. *International journal of current research and academic review*, 52-56.
- Rook, D. (1987). "The buying impulse". *Journal of Consumer Research*, 14 , 189-199.
- Rowley, J. (2001). *Information Marketing*. Oxon: Routledge.
- Samuel, N. (2021, August 19). Retrieved from <https://latana.com/post/branding-affects-consumer-behavior/>
- Shabir, S. (2021, June 11). Retrieved from <https://technologytimes.pk/2021/06/11/top-5-most-selling-smartphone-brands-in-pakistan-may-21/>
- Sharma, M. (2014). The impact on consumer buying behaviour: Cognitive dissonance. *Global Journal of Finance and Management*,, 833-840. doi:10.1016/S0148
- Social Class and Buying Behavior. (2017, July 18). Retrieved from https://ebookbou.edu.bd/Books/Text/SOB/MBA/mba_4321/Unit-07.pdf
- Socioeconomic Status. (2019). Retrieved from American Psychological Association: <https://www.apa.org/topics/socioeconomic-status>
- Spacey, J. (2015). Retrieved from <https://simplicable.com/new/brand-quality>
- Takeuchi, H., & Quelch, J. A. (1983, March 18). *Quality Is More than Making a Good Product*. Harvard Business Review. Retrieved from Research Leap: <https://researchleap.com/effects-of-brand-quality-brand-prestige-on-brand-purchase-intention-of-mobile-phone-brands-empirical-assessment-from-kenya/#:~:text=Brand%20quality%20is%20defined%20as,influence%20on%20consumer%20purchasing%20behavior.>
- Team, B. C. (2021). Habitual Buying - Meaning, Importance & Example. *mbaSkool*.
- Thompson, J. (2022, June 29). *Consumers Have Humanlike Relationships With Brands*. Retrieved from Business News Daily: <https://www.businessnewsdaily.com/2821-consumers-relationships-brands.html>
- WHAT IS A SOCIAL CLASS - CONSUMER BEHAVIOUR. (2021). Retrieved from Wisdom jobs: <https://www.wisdomjobs.com/e-university/consumer-behaviour-tutorial-94/what-is-a-social-class-10500.html>
- Wisnblit, L. G. (2015). Consumer Perception. In L. G. Wisnblit, *Consumer Behavior*. Pearson.
- Wood, W. (2009, June 09). *The Habitual Consumer*. Retrieved from Journal of Consumer Psychology: https://dornsife.usc.edu/assets/sites/545/docs/Wendy_Wood_Research_Articles/Habits/wood.neal.2009._the_habitual_consumer.pdf